

An Armor Against Covid-19, Could Alpha 1 Antitrypsin Be The One?

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Abstract

Since the COVID-19 pandemic alarm caused by the severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS)-coronavirus (CoV) 2 several institutions and agencies have attempted to find an explanation for the viral virulence and infectivity to contain it is spread. The fast propagation of this virus has contributed to an unprecedented rise in the number of cases worldwide. COVID-19 virus is highly contagious that spreads through droplets, respiratory secretions, and direct contact. This enveloped, single-stranded RNA virus has a specific envelop region called s region encoding (S protein), that specifically binds to the host cell receptor. Viral infection requires the participation of receptors on the surface of the host cell membrane. This is the key- step for the viral invasion of susceptible cells. Recently, results from the Italian alpha 1 antitrypsin Registry revealed a close geographic distribution of positive cases similar to the one recorded for SARS -CoV-2 infection. Patients who were AAT deficient presented with the highest infection rates, which drew attention to alpha 1 antitrypsin AAT role in COVID-19 infection. Alpha 1 antitrypsin deficiency (AATD) is certainly the most common genetic condition in adults characterized by decreased serum levels or defective AAT function, which raises the risk of developing many diseases, particularly pulmonary emphysema and cirrhosis of the liver. This review will discuss the main immunological properties that AAT has as a protective agent against the infection and their possible therapeutic application in clinical practice.

1. Introduction

Alpha1-Antitrypsin (AAT) is a serine protease inhibitor, whose primary role is to suppress the proteolytic activity of human neutrophil elastase in the lung. Alpha 1 antitrypsin is produced by the endoplasmic reticulum and released by the Golgi apparatus and displayed in hepatic cells, neutrophils, placental cytotrophoblasts, the endothelial lining of blood vessels, and pulmonary alveolar cells^{1,2}. The mean-secreted liver concentration is approximately < 3.5 mg/ml pre-day. When a tissue injury occurs or an acute inflammatory response is triggered, the serum level of AAT in the blood is increased by 6-fold coordinating local and systemic inflammation. As neutrophil recruiting continues, serum proteinases are poured, causing collateral tissue injury, AAT will set balance prevents a repeated cycle of self-injury³.

Alpha 1 antitrypsin deficiency (AATD) is a genetic acquired metabolic alignment characterized by reduced serum levels or diminished AAT function^{2,4}. The deficiency of AAT is defined as a disease of protease-antiprotease deficiency in the lungs, it is increasingly understood that AATD is an inflammatory condition. This inflammation is mainly driven by neutrophils and there are many alpha-1 antitrypsin-related pathways to intensify this neutrophil reaction^{5,6,7}.

The basis for AAT augmentation therapy (purified human protein) in AATD is to restore antiprotease equilibrium in the lungs, AAT replacement therapy was licensed by the United States Food and Drug Administration (FDA) in 1987, however, its potential benefits are also systemic, suggesting the possible use of alpha-1 antitrypsin in many inflammatory conditions^{8,9,10,11}.

Therapeutic strategies for AAT therapy have been revised over the last decade and appear to reach beyond the defense of lung tissue from neutrophilia-induced elastase injury intending to promote a healthy, anti-inflammatory, immunomodulatory activity. Interestingly, augmentation treatment has been applied to persons with normal AAT genetically non-deficient, it resolves steroid-refractory graft-versus-host complications^{12,13}. Preclinical trials also demonstrate the gain in multiple sclerosis, rheumatoid arthritis, type 2 diabetes, acute myocardial infarction, and stroke as well. Being a hereditary disease, it shows geographic variation, AATD was observed to have the greatest incidence rate in northern Italy, Spain, and Iran^{14,15}.

Pathophysiology and mode of protection

Alpha-1-antitrypsin (AAT) is considered a major inhibitor of serum protease, which acutely blocks the proteolytic enzymes-facilitated entry of COVID-19 which is found in serum and bronchoalveolar tissues,

indicating that its effects are biologically important as part of a normal defense strategy against COVID-19 infection and severe lung injury^{16,17}.

Low serum AAT levels were correlated with the severity of COVID-19 infection and IL-6, a cytokine identified in the disease course as a biomarker for severity. The unique anti-inflammatory, immunomodulatory, and anti-coagulation activity of AAT has important effects on the pathophysiology of the disease and possible therapeutic role^{18,19}.

Alpha 1 antitrypsin a transmembrane serine protease 2 inhibitor

Cell invasion of COVID-19 viruses relies on the coupling of viral spike (S) proteins to cell receptors. Furthermore, SARS-CoV-2 uses the ACE2 receptor for entrance²⁰. Before it can bind to this receptor, the virus needs to prime them, transmembrane serine protease 2 (TMPRSS2) is the major protease required for the priming of protein S; a crucial step in cell invasion. Discrepancies in the severity of infection, virulence, and spread have been implied to depend on host proteases. There have been claims that disparity in protease-antiprotease could have a crucial role in the pathogenesis and infectivity of SARS-CoV-2. Therapeutic trials incorporating TMPRSS2 inhibitors have shown promising effects since they blocked viral entry^{21,22}.

Alpha 1 antitrypsin is indeed a novel inhibitor of TMPRSS2 that is anchored to an extracellular domain of TMPRSS2 in such a configuration that is appropriate for catalytic activities. The inhibitory activity of AAT was identified in the SARS-CoV-2 viral loading system^{13,21}. Low serum AAT levels were associated with severe COVID-19 infection. Besides, a high prevalence of AATD in North Italy was suggested to be the leading cause of the disastrous effects of coronavirus infections. AAT prevents H3N2 influenza A and B virus infections in the murine model, although these viruses do not need TMPRSS2 priming, which reinforced the idea that AAT can mediate anti-viral effects via multiple mechanisms in immunity against COVID-19^{13,21,23,24}.

Alpha 1 antitrypsin And Neutrophils

Alpha 1 antitrypsin inhibits neutrophil elastase and proteinase. Neutrophil elastase enzyme catalyzes numerous structural proteins in the lungs and handles numerous innate immune mediators, recently implicated in the pathogenicity of the SARS-CoV-2 substrate by cleavage the S1-S2 junction of the viral S protein, where the coronavirus spike protein (S) plays a key role in the early steps of viral infection, with the S1 domain responsible for receptor binding and the S2 domain mediating membrane fusion^{25,26}.

The elevated neutrophil level was observed in patients with COVID-19 with serious illness relative to those with mild infection and healthy control. What supports AAT activity is the distinguished neutrophil inflammation seen in pneumonia patients lacking AAT genetic defined AATD, similar to autopsy results in patients with COVID-19 pneumonia, implying a shared pathological mechanism^{27,28}.

Neutrophil extracellular traps (NETs) are components of the innate immune response to neutralize invading pathogens, it is called a double-bladed sword since the toxicity of NETs' exposes the host endothelial cells and parenchymal tissue to extensive damage^{29,30,31}. Unbalanced NET formation and neutrophil triggering can contribute to many ailments, including sepsis, thrombosis, acute lung injury, kidney diseases, and hypertension. AAT controls neutrophilia and it is neutrophil extracellular traps, making an important step in reducing the COVID-19 course and comorbidities^{31,32}.

Alpha 1 antitrypsin and Alveolar Macrophages

To understand the effect of AAT in alveolar macrophages we should know what apoptosis; a form of programmed cell death where distinctive biochemical and cellular changes occur eventually ends in death. Apoptosis creates cell fragments named "apoptotic bodies" the phagocytic cells could engulf and eliminate before the membrane integrity is broken³³. Removing those apoptotic cells by phagocytic cells is called efferocytosis 'burying of dead cells'. It prevents tissue exposure to toxic enzymes, oxidants, and other intracellular components such as proteases^{34,35}. AAT improves alveolar macrophages (AM) engulfment power (phagocytosis) and efferocytosis thus decreases α -TNF release along with other pro-inflammatory markers furthermore it reduces levels of pro-inflammatory cytokine secreted in the sputum^{1,36,37}.

Additionally, AAT was identified in the bronchial secretion proved to be capable of neutralizing COVID-19, indicating that it could pass to the lungs and it may be present in the area of invasion and replication of SARS-CoV-2^{38,39}.

Alpha 1 antitrypsin and Bronchial Secretion

Wettstein L. et al ⁴⁰screened bronchoalveolar lavage and by Western Blots, he identified AAT as a unique inhibitor of SARS-CoV-2, it tackles the viral spike protein and blocks SARS-CoV-2 infection of the individual airway epithelium, that is the first natural defense toward infection³⁸. Not only as a physical shield by the mucociliary apparatus, but also through the epithelial lining fluid with immunological activity^{41,42}. This fluid is high in innate immune peptides and proteins of antibacterial and antiviral functions, such as lysozyme, lactoferrin. In the alveolar fluid, AAT will suppress the inhaled contaminated droplets and aerosols from infecting respiratory tract cells. Infection is usually restricted to the upper respiratory tract, leading to a mild symptom. The serious disease is caused by viral spread to the lungs resulting in acute respiratory distress syndrome, cytokine storm, multi-organ failure, septic shock, and death^{38,43}.

Alpha 1 antitrypsin and Complement System

Viruses tend to engage with complements receptors and components to avoid host-defense mechanisms. Complement is a crucial player in defense against infections, however, its excessive or defective activation can lead to collateral tissue damage. Most critically ill COVID-19 patients will develop impairment of lung function due to an immunity response derangement rather than elevated virus load^{44,45}. The release of pro-inflammatory cytokines and the extravasation of blood neutrophils and monocytes contribute to disrupted air-blood barrier by inducing collateral tissue injury, in particular to bronchial epithelial cells and endothelial vascular cells. In addition, damage to endothelial vascular cells has been accredited for thrombotic microangiopathy^{46,47}. As we know that C3 plays a central role in the activation of the complement system C3a is an anaphylatoxin and the precursor of some cytokines and C3b serves as an opsonizing agent^{48,49,50}. Reports have demonstrated widespread complement stimulation, detected by C3a generation and C3-fragment deposition in lung biopsy samples from patients with severe COVID-19. In addition to a significant increase in C5a serum concentrations^{51,52,53}. Another defense mechanism of AAT is through complement protein, C3b has increased the phagocytosis of opsonized pathogenic bacteria through the complementary receptor pathway. Cleavage of the C3 component of the complement system is the key step in its activation, if protease activity exists as in the case of neutrophilic derived infection, C3 will degrade by the proteolytic effect and render complement in-active⁵⁴. The result is impaired immunological response of the body to the offending pathogen. AAT is a neutrophilic-protease inhibitor that can set the balance and protect the complement C3 component from degradation by dysregulated protease activity this set the way for a new role for AAT during acute inflammation to the pulmonary tract in both deficient and non-deficient patients^{55,56}.

Alpha 1 antitrypsin and Serum Fibrinogen

Fibrinogen is well recognized as a *chronic obstructive pulmonary disease* biomarker used for assessing severity, exacerbation, and mortality in patients with chronic obstructive airway disease^{57,58}. Blood fibrinogen degradation product is elevated in AATD patients, suggesting severe airflow obstruction, and tend to decrease in patients on AAT augmentation therapy⁵⁹. Similarly, results indicated that it is a useful disease activity marker in patients with severe COVID-19 infection⁶⁰.

Advantages of AAT Augmentation Therapy

The possible therapeutic antiviral activities of AAT in SARS-CoV-2 infection were evaluated. Introducing AAT during COVID-19 infection has decreased the viral load and replication in the target cells and tissues, such as salivary glands, which have major pathological effects for viral dissemination. Thus, it is safe to say, AAT does not only limit disease severity in affected persons but also limits the epidemiological spread of the virus to others^{61,62}.

Therapeutic AAT activity was equivalent to the activity of camostat, a drug recently used in COVID-19 that prevents SARS-CoV-2 cell entry by modifying cell permeability, on the other hand, AAT prevents extracellular proteases exhibits his activities in the cell's exterior^{21,63,64}.

Azouz NP et al⁶² present proof that extracellular protease activity is rate-limiting within the SARS-CoV-2 cell entry phase ⁶². Implying that it will provide a good platform to impede SARS-CoV-2 entry and modify the exterior of the host cell. The frustrating reports of hydroxychloroquine, which interact with the function of intracellular cathepsins in drug testing and in vitro analysis, are further compatible with the key role of extracellular proteases^{65,66}.

Camostat as an antiviral drug may quickly lose potency due to the high number of mutations occurring in the viral genome, not to mention the intracellular effect of camostat which might lead to unintended inhibition of intracellular protease. Another benefit of AAT; that targeted extracellular host proteases [TMPRSS2]^{61,67}.

Slamming the door in front of the virus instead of killing it along with infected cells is a safer strategy. Treatment with purified human AAT significantly increases efferocytosis, phagocytosis, and total alveolar macrophage scavenging activity^{35,68}. Compromised scavenging activity result in pathogen persistence, bacterial colonization of the lower airways attributing to inflammation, tissue destruction, and frequent exacerbations^{1,68,69}.

Moreover, dead cells in the lung alveoli will induce local tissue damage that will set for acute respiratory distress syndrome. Clearing those Infected dead cells by the pyroptosis process that will trigger a cytokine

release, and in severe cases, cytokine storm and intravascular thrombosis auscultate the disease severity. All are ominous prognostic factors for patients' survival^{27,34,70,71}.

Purified human AAT infusion to deficient individuals at physiological dose can decrease inflammatory cytokine release and minimize damage to the lung after bacterial infections. Infusion in non-genetic AAT patients decreased post-translational changes to the AAT native molecule, resulting in an "acquired" functional AAT-deficient case. A condition noticed following environmental exposure to cigarette and pathogens, the supplement with native AAT was suggested to regain normal functional AAT levels in severe airway disease^{72,73,74,76}.

Convalescence serum shows substantial suppression of SARS-CoV-2 entry. In the convalescent plasma therapies, the abundance of AAT in donated plasma can play an additional defensive role as non-immunoglobulin components⁷⁷. Convalescent plasma treatment is effective for its users. Although the main benefits are credited to neutralizing antibodies, minor benefits from the transition of the intravenous immunoglobulin (IVIG) standard indicate that the IgG antibody is not the only serum ingredient that can play a significant role in reducing the stress of COVID-19 in patients⁷⁸.

Conclusion

Alpha 1 antitrypsin can act as a natural inhibitor of SARS-CoV-2 infection, especially among severe cases as concentrations of AAT raise. Its extraordinary activity in both elements of animal and cellular immunity in the protection against infection form the foundation for its application as a therapeutic agent. Moreover, AAT will not only limit disease severity in affected persons but also limits the epidemiological spread of the virus to others via respiratory secretion which forms a potential assay for vaccine production.

We recommend introducing AAT in the panel of drugs against COVID-19 as it can reduce the severe cases and reduce transmission rate with a good safety profile. It will be interesting therefore to investigate whether the levels of AAT in the lungs or serum of COVID-19 patients are adversely associated with virus load or disease progression. There are still unresolved chapters in the life cycle of the virus that need a great deal of work to properly grasp the course and consequences of the outbreak, and AAT is a promising option in this sense.

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